

Light Pollution is an Environmental Issue

Plenary Lecture

Avalon Owens¹

DOI:

Abstract: For millions of years, the only lights visible at night were the moon, the stars, and bioluminescent life (mostly fireflies). Almost every organism on earth evolved to thrive within perfectly reliable cycles of natural light and natural dark that are today in total disarray. By radically transforming the nocturnal landscape, artificial light at night disrupts the development, movement, foraging, and reproduction of diverse species including sea turtles, migratory birds, and nocturnal pollinators. In this talk, Dr. Avalon Owens (The Rowland Institute at Harvard - owenslab.org) reviews the many ways in which light pollution threatens urban and rural ecosystems alike, with potentially disastrous consequences for biological life. She concludes by highlighting a few simple things that we can all do to protect the night sky, fireflies, and natural systems worldwide.

Keywords: disruption of wildlife; nocturnal ecosystems; conservation of natural darkness.

Corresponding Author: avalonceleste@gmail.com

¹The Rowland Institute, Harvard University, USA